

Director's Message

Patrick McCarthy

As we approach the end of 2022, we can look back at an eventful year — too eventful in many respects. A number of unplanned events, some under our control and some not, interrupted operations at one or another of our sites in 2022. Despite these challenges, the scientific output of our user community remains high and the impact of our facilities continues to grow. New instruments and new software will expand the power of NOIRLab, for new observations as well as analysis of archival data and cross-platform research.

Earlier this year Dennis Crabtree (NRC Herzberg Astronomy & Astrophysics) updated his assessment of the scientific impact of various telescopes. All of our large telescopes continue to rank highly, but the Blanco 4m telescope at CTIO stood out as the telescope with the highest fraction of high-impact papers, largely due to the Dark Energy Camera (DECam). Astro Data Lab is making it possible for the entire community to use the DECam archival data and the range of science done with DECam continues to expand beyond the Dark Energy Survey, with high-impact programs in Solar System science, galactic structure, time-domain astronomy,

and emission-line galaxies, to name but a few. Congratulations to the DECam team!

The publication rate for the International Gemini Observatory remains high, with little apparent impact from the pandemic and other challenges in Hawai'i and Chile. The steady stream of new instruments in the pipeline ensures that Gemini's impact will continue to grow throughout the decade. Many of the science highlights in 2022, particularly from Gemini, Blanco, and SOAR, come from the time domain. Rapid response to both targets of opportunity and novel ideas has enabled teams to conduct time-critical observations ranging from moving objects in the Solar System to distant quasars and GRBs. The ANTARES time-domain event broker is operating smoothly in collaboration with the LCOGT network as we build out our time-domain astronomy ecosystem in anticipation of the start of Rubin operations in late 2024.

NOIRLab conducted its first Lab-wide hiring campaign for science staff in 2021/2022. The result is an incoming class of ten scientists distributed across all sites. It is a highly diverse group of early career scientists that brings new energy and expertise to NOIRLab (see article in this issue).

Climate change is here and it affects astronomy

Perhaps the most dramatic impact of climate change on astronomy is the increasing number of wildfires near observatories. As recent studies¹ have shown, wildfires became larger and more frequent since the 2000s. In June of this year, a wildfire swept through Arizona's Baboquivari Mountains, home to Kitt Peak National Observatory. As detailed in the article by Michelle Edwards et al. in this issue of *The Mirror* (and the cover image), the fire destroyed a number of buildings on the mountain and damaged critical infrastructure. Thanks to heroic efforts by the firefighting crew, no scientific structures were significantly damaged. Six months on, however, we are still struggling to bring power, data, and roads back to pre-fire operational levels. Kitt Peak is not the first observatory to experience a wildfire: the tragic fire at Mt. Stromlo in Australia and fires at Mt. Graham, Mt.

¹*Science Advances*, 16 March 2022, doi:10.1126/sciadv.abc0020

Wilson, and others are a sign that the threat of fire is more serious than ever, and that we must remain prepared.

Just a month after Kitt Peak had its near brush with disaster, a once-in-30-year snowstorm hit Cerro Tololo and Cerro Pachón, forcing the evacuation of both mountains and the loss of power for extended periods. Fast action by our facilities teams ensured that everyone was safe and that instruments were warmed in a controlled manner. In July we were in the unusual situation in which one of our sites was closed due to fire and another due to snow and ice.

At NOIRLab we are committed to doing our part to help combat climate change. The NOIRLab Sustainability Program guides our approach to reducing air travel, improving the efficiency of electrical appliances, phasing out fossil fuel vehicles, and most urgently, installing photovoltaic (PV) systems at our observatory sites. This year we began a project that will make Gemini South carbon neutral by installing an additional 800 kilowatts of PV power just off the summit at Cerro Pachón (see the article by Inger Jorgensen and Piero Anticono in this issue). An NSF award supports the development of the solar power farm, and a proposal for a battery pack to support nighttime operations has been submitted. Construction will begin early next year.

Our Sustainability Program targets an overall CO₂ reduction of 50% relative to 2019 levels across all of NOIRLab. This is just a start towards our goal to achieve net zero in conjunction with local, state, and national utilities in Chile, Hawai'i, and Arizona.

Not all of our challenges in 2022 can be ascribed to climate change; some have been rooted in the unprecedented interruption of infrequent but critical operational tasks. In October of this year, an operational error led to glass-to-metal contact on the edge of the Gemini North primary mirror during washing and stripping in preparation for recoating. Fortunately, the damage to the mirror was minor and outside of the clear aperture. Such events require a stand-down and careful investigation and analysis. An external Incident Review Board is leading the investigation. The plan to treat the chip on the edge of the mirror is coming together, and we expect to return Gemini North to operations in early 2023 with no expected loss of performance.

The commercialization of space is growing and impacting astronomy from the ground

The launch of large constellations of near-Earth orbiting (NEO) satellites is changing the night sky. The deployment of

thousands, then tens of thousands, and ultimately potentially hundreds of thousands of NEO communications satellites will impact nearly all celestial observations from the ground, particularly those from wide-field imaging systems like DECam and Rubin Observatory. NOIRLab, IAU's Center for the Protection of Dark and Quiet Skies, the AAS, and other bodies are working with satellite vendors, regulatory agencies, and engineering teams to find solutions — hardware, software, and regulatory — that will reduce the impact of the satellites on astronomy while allowing the service providers to carry out their mission of improving communications worldwide. Good progress has been made with Starlink, and conversations are progressing with other providers. The launch of the prototype AST Bluewalker 3 satellite in late 2022 heralds a new entrant — large-area cell phone towers in space. Early observations² show that when fully unfolded, the Bluewalker 3 satellites have visual magnitudes ranging from 0 to +4. The impact of the AST Bluewalker 3 satellites on radio astronomy may be even larger than the impact on optical astronomy.

The satellite constellations also complicate the operation of laser beacons for adaptive optics. We are making good progress in this area; look for a public announcement around the time of the January 2023 AAS meeting.

Returning to normal?

As we are learning to live with the COVID-19 pandemic, NOIRLab, like much of the world, is searching for a “new normal” in the way we work and interact with the scientific community. We have been delighted to support in-person science meetings in the second half of 2022. The Gemini Science Meeting in Seoul, the Rubin Project & Community Workshop, and the “DECam at 10 years — Looking Back, Looking Forward” conference in Tucson were all great successes. We were happy to see our colleagues in person, and we were reminded of the unique value that in-person interactions provide.

Our daily work has evolved from mostly remote to hybrid, with staff who are not required on-site coming to the office up to five days each week, with agreements from their managers. While these hybrid work agreements do accommodate the particular needs of each staff member and their teams, there is little doubt that something is lost when we are not able to meet in person, to think together around the whiteboard, to talk over coffee and during lunch, or to have that spontaneous conversation in the hallway. The debate around the right mix of remote versus on-site work will continue for some time.

² <https://noirlab.edu/public/announcements/ann22033/>

Director's Message

Science is a collaborative enterprise; I hope that we can rekindle more of the collaborative spirit and free-form creative dialog within our teams as we find our optimal new normal mode of working together.

The future is closer than it appears

The 2010 and 2020 decadal survey reports laid out exciting priorities for ground-based OIR astronomy and for the national centers. Rubin Observatory is one of the outcomes from the 2010 survey, and it is now in the final stages of

construction. The 2020 survey recommended a bi-hemispheric system of Extremely Large Telescopes. An important step toward realizing that goal occurs in December and January when the US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP) components, the Thirty Meter Telescope and Giant Magellan Telescope projects, conduct their first NSF design reviews. The NSF Preliminary Design Review will examine the technical status of the telescope projects along with their schedules and project execution plans. A review of the NOIRLab role in the US-ELTP will be held in mid-2023. Stay tuned.

Aerial panorama of Cerro Pachón in Chile, with the Vera C. Rubin Observatory visible in the middle. The image release can be [found here](#).

Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/T. Matsopoulos